

Fast-Track Your Knowledge of the Forecasting Budget project

Current Budgeting Workflow (Estimated time: 5 minutes)

- Managing the cash flow of a large research group involves two elements:
 - **Expenses:** bills categorised by different types (e.g. Equipment, travel, research etc.) and payment date deadlines.
 - **Funding:** sources categorised by one or more types with strict rules on certain categories it can cover with validity dates (effective date and expiration date)
- Example: Fund A funds salary and has a value of \$10,000 and is valid from 1st January to 31st December 2026, and Fund B can fund both salary and travel, and has a value of \$5000. Expense A requests for funding in salary of \$5,000 by 5th May and Expense B requests for funding in travel of \$5,000 by 16th August.
 - Fund A should be able to allocate \$5,000 to Expense A because it asks for salary fund, similarly, Fund B should allocate \$5000 to Expense B.
 - Leftover of Fund A cannot be allocated to Expense B because it cannot fund travel expenses.
 - If accidentally allocate Fund B to Expense A, it will left Fund B unfunded
 - If we have hundreds of funds and expenses, it is likely we cannot find the optimal combination of fund allocation
- **Purpose of this project:** How do we maximise the number of expenses paid, especially the important ones, while strictly adhering to funding rules and temporal constraints?

High-level Architecture and Workflow (Estimated time: 15 minutes)

Overview:

- Users log their fundings and expenses data via web applications or Excel spreadsheets.
- Users choose which expense is prioritised.
- Users generate a budget allocation and forecast the status of fundings and expenses

A detailed description of the requirements for the budgeting and forecasting tool builds in R Shiny can be found in the user stories document: [User Stories](#), (Estimated time: 20 minutes)

Workflow (Estimated time: 5 minutes):

How the System Fits Together **(Estimated time: 10 minutes):**

Algorithm -simplify-situation (Estimated time: 30 minutes)

To do: Open GitHub code [Algorithm Code](#) with this section

Step 1: Primary Optimisation (Full Allocation)

The first phase creates an architecture to optimise fund distribution using two key elements: an Objective Function and Constraint Functions.

1) The Objective Function (Prioritisation)

This determines the order in which funds are distributed based on user-defined priority. The goal is to fully fund higher-priority expenses before addressing lower-priority ones.

- **Logic:** Ranking is determined by the priority labelled by the user.
- **In R:** This is controlled by the weight vector (*weights*) inside the objective function:

$$\text{set_objective}(\text{sum_expr}(\text{weights}[j] * y[j], j = 1:n_expenses), \text{max})$$

2) The Constraint Functions (Rules)

These functions ensure that funds are used strictly within their allowed scope.

- **Logic:** Funds must match the allowed expense category and fall within the valid date window:

$$\text{ValidFrom} \leq \text{LPD} \leq \text{ValidTo}$$

Constraints also prevent overpayment or missed payments.

- **In R:** The constraints functions (*add_constraint()*) are defined inside the *model < - MIPModel()* function.

Step 2: Residual Optimisation (Partial Fulfillment)

To maximise budget utilisation, the algorithm executes a second phase. Unlike Step 1, which focuses on full allocations, this step manages "leftover" funds to ensure no capacity is wasted.

1) The "Greedy" Algorithm:

The system iteratively matches any remaining budget in funding sources against unfunded expenses, moving from top priority down to the lowest.

2) Validity Constraint:

We have made one change to the time constraint compared to Step 1: a partial payment is only attempted if the expense category matches and the date constraint is strictly satisfied:

$$LPD < ValidTo$$

(Note the strict inequality compared to Step 1)

- **In R:** The updated matching logic is handled by *time_match_modified*. This aggressively reduces the balance for high-priority items that weren't fully funded in Step 1 and the actual filling is performed by the *apply_greedy_fill* function.

The full mathematical construction and detailed explanation of the set up can be found here: [Algorithm Logic Mathematics Full](#)

GitHub Repo Structure (Estimated time: 10 minutes)

Project [Module Structure](#) Correct as of 16/02/2026

These are modules required for the application to work. The modules structure as `module A ---> module B` indicates that `module A` calls function(s) in `module B`.

Function calls structure: [function_calls](#) (Estimated time: 30 minutes)

Technical Tools (Estimated time: 5 minutes)

Important packages used for most of the web app:

- R/Shiny: main frontend and backend
- Bslib: modern UI components (sidebar, card, value box...)
- DT: used to display data tables
- Openxlsx and readxl: used to read and write Excel spreadsheets
- Dplyr and tidyr: used to create and manipulate data
- Ompr: models mixed integer linear program (for allocation algorithm)
- ROI: optimizer for solving the MILP
- Plotly: used to create the interactive shortfall bar graph
- Chorddiag: used to create the interactive circos plot for budget allocation (started off with circlize library for a static circos plot)

Other helpful packages are also included but are minimally used for specific functions (more information in the packages section of [App.R](#) (Estimated time: 5 minutes))

Links

Test App: [Test App Link](#)

WEHI forecasting page: [WEHI Forecasting Project Landing Page](#)

Final presentation: [Forecasting Budget Summer 25-26 Final Presentation](#)

Manuals (User and Admin Manuals): [Manual folder](#)

Testing documentation: [Testing](#)

Project improvement: [Project Future Improvements](#)

GitHub repository: [GitHub Repository](#)

Project folder: [Summer 2025-2026](#)

Technical diary: [Technical Diary](#)

Wireframe: [Wireframe](#)